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Impact Of Capacity Building On Employee Service Delivery In Enugu State Civil Service Commission

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ABSTRACT

This study ascertained the impact of capacity building on employee service delivery in Enugu State Civil Service Commission. The specific objectives include to: ascertain the effect of capacity building on the quality of staff output in Enugu State Civil Service Commission, and examine the extent to which staff empowerment programmes affect employee commitment to organizational goal actualization in Enugu State Civil Service Commission. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Data generated through questionnaires administered to the respondents. Statistical analysis involves the organization and interpretation of data according to well-defined, systematic and mathematical procedures and rules. Data collected were presented using tables, means and simple frequency. The study revealed that capacity building plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of staff output within the Enugu State Civil Service Commission. Also, the study found that staff empowerment programs have a significant positive impact on employee commitment to organizational goal actualization in Enugu State Civil Service Commission. Based on the results, the study recommended among others that it is recommended that the Enugu State Civil Service Commission continues to invest in capacity building initiatives for its employees. These initiatives should be tailored to address specific skill gaps and job requirements.

Keywords: Capacity building, Employee service delivery, Quality of staff output and Staff empowerment programs

INTRODUCTION

Employees are the backbone of every organization. Of all the resources available “people” are the most important because they are needed to activate other resources. People are the main instrument for the attainment of the objectives of the organization (Nwankwo & Ogbaji, 2013). As an intangible factor, the human capital decides for all other tangible factors and their requisite deployment in the service of the organization. The tangible factor such as money and other physical factors can only be effectively converted and utilized at the discretion and directives of the intangible factor i.e. human capital (Ezeh, 2021). In the opinion of Dada (2017) the modern term ‘human resources’ and ‘human capital’ reflects the recognition of the importance of employees. Employees are seen less and less as an expensive necessity and more and more as a strategic resource that may provide an organization with competitive advantage. Every Organization is the summation of her human capital. Ravendu (2019) posits that, it is the human assets and not the fixed or tangible assets that differentiate an organization from its competitors. Human asset is the key intangible asset for any organization.

The essence of capacity building is to ensure that employees within the organization are highly qualified to meet up as well as tackle that organizational tasks and goals. Miller & Doherty (2016) Opined that

capacity building is the development of knowledge, attitude and skills of the workforce for enhancing the abilities to achieve the short-term and long-term goals on organizational as well as personal levels. Capacity building helps to ensure that the employees possess the knowledge and skills they need to perform their jobs effectively, take on new responsibilities and adapt to changing conditions (Jones and George, 2008).

Most Government Personnel also lack commitment to the organizational goals because of the notion that government business is no man's business. This notion has resulted to absurdities such misuse of resources/properties, waste, tardiness, insubordination, ineffectiveness, exploitation and bribery. They capitalize on every opportunity to make money, sit and wait for government allocation; feel reluctant to carry out their duties except their palms are greased. It must also be noted that Civil Servants also face a lot of difficulties in the discharge of their duties. Some of the trainings are not adequate/relevant to the present job or the evolutionary trend of the organization.

From available Literature, no research has been carried to examine the effect of capacity building on employee service delivery in Enugu State Civil Service Commission between 2015– 2022.

The broad objective of this study is to assess the impact of capacity building on employee service delivery in Enugu State Civil Service Commission. The specific objectives include:

1. To ascertain the effect of capacity building on the quality of staff output in Enugu State Civil Service Commission.
2. To examine the extent to which staff empowerment programmes affect employee commitment to organizational goal actualization in Enugu State Civil Service Commission

Conceptual Review

Capacity Building

According to FY (2012), capacity building is an evidence-driven process of strengthening the abilities of individuals, organizations and systems to perform core functions sustainably and to continue to improve and develop overtime. From the definition, FY sees capacity building to entail a process of continuous improvement in the system to effectively perform tasks.

Miller and Doherty (2016), referred to capacity building as the development of knowledge, attitude and skills of the workforce for enhancing the abilities to achieve the short-term and long-term goals on organizational as well as personal levels. According to this, capacity building covers the inabilities of all employees and develops the desirable skills and attitude which enable them accomplish suitable tasks efficiently.

Capacity building is a systematic approach of developing and enhancing employee skills, abilities, and knowledge for the purpose of increasing organizational effectiveness (Aguinus & Kraiger, 2009). Like many scholars, Aguinus & Kraiger perceive capacity building as element that gives fluidity, flexibility, and functionality to an organization. In the opinion of Fletcher et al (2016), capacity building has a significant impact on employee performance and employee retention. It is associated with intention to stay which is mediated by three different work attitudes: job satisfaction, employee engagement and change related anxiety.

Employee Service Delivery

Delivering quality service means following best practices like valuing customers' time, having a pleasant attitude, and providing knowledgeable and resourceful resources (Catherine, 2022). It is considered as an essential strategy for success and survival. Service according to Cambridge Dictionary refers to a government system or private organization that is responsible for a particular type of activity, or providing a particular thing that people need.

Services are deeds, performance or efforts that cannot physically be possessed (Matariano, 2005). Stauss (2005) also argues that services are not physical resources but economic transactions exchanged for money, comprising exchange of specialized skills and knowledge.

Hollensen (2013) explains that variability infers that services are rarely the same because they involve interaction with people. The organization for economic Co-operation and Development (2010) opined,

service delivery can be categorized in a number of ways including, the type of entity providing them, the type of user and the nature of the services provided. The categories of services include private services, public services and collective or joint services. Public services imply services provided by government or where governments have significance influence, perhaps by providing funds. It involves those services directly provided by some level of government such as police protection and other areas of public management such as health, education, defense, justice (Humphreys, 1998).

Between 1914 and 1954, the Nigerian colonial government was not directly involved in the provision of public services. They played a variety of functions, including defense, setting performance criteria, creating model institutions, and providing funding to commercial service providers. The general evaluation of Nigeria's public service delivery is below average. Even without using any research or literature, the failure of Nigeria Airways, the disintegration of the Nigerian Railway system, the unpredictable electricity supply, the ongoing strikes by university professors and health workers, among other things, validate the subpar ranking (Fagbemi, 2006).

Capacity Building and the Quality of Employee Output

Capacity building according to Barney (2001) is much more than training, and includes; human resource development which involves the process of equipping individuals with skills, understanding, access to information, knowledge and training which enables them to perform effectively. The main goal of employees' development is to help the organization achieve its' mission and business goals (Pinninton & Edwards, 2018). Employee development and training are indispensable components of strategic human resources management as well as a means of reducing uncertainty in the market place and achieving organizational goals. According to Hamidianpour, Esmaeilpour and Zarei (2016), untrained workers could make mistakes and might not deliver quality service to customers, which might negatively affect the overall organizational performance Sultana et al, (2012) believes that capacity building is a process of expansion of knowledge, skills and techniques and it is mandatory for employees to get requisite training for perfectly completion of job. Capacity building here is perceived as necessary part of the total quality management process as it increases the technical and social competency of the employees. Obisi (2011) suggests that training is mandatory for every employee as it is difficult to acquire skill and acknowledge without training and with unskilled labour, it is very difficult for the organization to survive. Certain services need to be provided or supplied by people with specific knowledge and skills in order for them to be carried out effectively. Due to this, the majority of firms have turned to employee development in order to accomplish effective service delivery. This can be accomplished by offering thorough on-the-job training, sufficient incentive, appropriate direction, consulting support, and other capacity-building programs. Current organizations are facing extensive competition, continuously changing technological and business environment. Globalization and ever changing customer needs have added up more challenges on business organizations. In order to meet these challenges, the industries are seeking to reach its targeted profit level by ensuring proper training and development of employees. Employees are most precious asset for any company as they can build up or destroy reputation of company and they can effect profitability (Elnaga and Imran, 2013).

Fullan (2007) opined that employees' training equips employees with skills that enable them to become more efficient and productive workers. Employees who are well-trained often have higher motivation and moral because they feel that the company has invested in their ability and development. If employee is satisfied with the organization, then his performance level will also increase and he will work with more zeal and dedication for the betterment of the entire organization (Mba, 2016). In line with this, Normah and Othman (2012), observes that giving employees opportunity for training in an organization does not only motivate them but also help them to further learn their required and expected task which increases their work performance and exposes them to believe that they are part and parcel of the organization.

Ngure and Njiru (2013) stated that many public organizations have now adopted employee capacity building as a means of improving the quality, efficiency and speed of public service delivery. The Director General of employment during a three day workshop for officers of human resources and other

staff agency on Wednesday 5th February 2022 stated that developing the capacities of workers in government ministries, departments and agencies is key to efficient service delivery.

Empirical Literature

Capacity building has been identified by various scholars and anchors to be very crucial for employee service delivery for the effectiveness of an organization. In the light of the above, Okonkwo (2022) conducted a research on Capacity Building and Employee Performance in Plastic Manufacturing companies in Anambra State. The study collected data from both primary and secondary sources. Three hypotheses were generated and Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in testing the hypothesis. The study concludes that capacity building has a significant positive relationship with employee performance in plastic manufacturing companies in Anambra State.

Aku et al, (2021) conducted a research on Capacity Building and Employees' Performance in Dr Isa Mustapha Agwai I Polytechnic, Lafia. Two research questions, objectives and hypotheses were formulated for the study. In this study, capacity building is measured with training and education, while employees' performance is measured with productivity. Yamane's sample size determination formula was used in the study to obtain a sample size of 155 for the study. Both primary and secondary data were used. The 155 copies of questionnaire were administered to the teaching staff across the schools that constitute the Polytechnic. Data were analyzed based on Karl Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). Descriptive Statistics and frequencies were also performed on the data. The two research questions raised were analyzed using simple percentage and the hypotheses formulated were also tested at 05% confidence interval. The major Findings in the study are that; there are significant positive relationships between training, education and productivity in Dr Isa Mustapha Agwai I Polytechnic, Lafia. Thus, conclusion drawn is that capacity building plays a significant role in improving the performance in terms of training and education of the academic staff of the Polytechnic.

Mobaral et al (2019) conducted a research on impact of training and development on employees' performance. Data were gathered from sampled respondents. A total number of 30 (thirty) employees were selected to provide answers to the structured questionnaire. The findings of this research study and the subsequent evaluation carried out on the responses reflect the key areas of training and development and its challenges on employee performance, motivation, retention and morale. From the chart presented, 15 responds out of 30 strongly agreed that training and development program has positive impact to develop organization while 7 respondents just agreed but 5 respondents do not agree with this, 3 respondents remain neutral. It can be said that training has high influential impact on employee performance.

Al-Mustapha (2017) examined the effectiveness of human resources development of construction firms in North Western Nigeria using a total of 360 structured questionnaires. The variable was tested using ANOVA- F and mean score under five sub-heading (information and communication issues, organizational productivity, corporate performance, and organizational culture and staff turnover). The findings of the study revealed that HRD strategies adopted showed strong improvement on: performance, minimized wastage, and ease of handling development challenges enhance corporate loyalty, construction planning and design, group thinking and desire for professional growth followed.

Ampomah (2016) examined the effect of training and development on employee productivity in a private tertiary institution in Ghana. The study used the simple random sampling technique to select staff from all levels of management. A high response rate of ninety-six percent was obtained using the personal method of data collection, based on which the analysis was made using the frequency tables and charts. The study found out that employees are aware of the purpose of training in the organization, the training objectives are clear to them before the training as well as the selection criteria. The study also found out that employees are motivated through training; and training and development results into higher performance.

Ohaeri and Chukwu (2016) in their research manpower and employee service delivery; a study of Enugu State Local Government Service Commission. The main purpose of this study is to examine the effect of manpower development on employees' service delivery in Enugu State Local Government Service

Commission. The study is a descriptive research. The researcher adopted a survey design. Based on the findings, the staff do not enjoy services or benefits given for staff training in local government. Training shows significant increase in service delivery and organizational performance in the local government. He concluded the training improves the drive, initiative, quality of work of the employees thus assist them to be more committed in achieving the goals and objectives of the organization and this has the tendency of enhancing effectiveness among workers within an organization. Therefore, training should be based on the needs of the organization and benefit the employee in terms of performance and knowledge which in turn affect the organization. Training assessment should provide a clear understanding of the difference between current and expected performance. Performance discrepancies should be identified and action plans developed to improve performance of employees.

In the research conducted by Neelam et al (2014) titled the Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance and Productivity: A study of United Bank Limited Peshawar City, KPK, and Pakistan. The objective of the study was to investigate the impact of training and development on employee's performance and productivity. Eight United Banks were selected for the study. Eighty Questionnaires were distributed for data collection. Data were analyzed and discussed. The result showed that there was significant relationship between the variables, the independent variables. Training and development have a positive impact on Employee's performance and productivity.

The study "Capacity building and development of employees in Federal Road Safety Corps' conducted by FRSC (2014) examined the impact of capacity building on operational capabilities of public sector organization. The research adopted the survey research design with 250 respondents as its simple size. The three null hypotheses were rejected and the alternatives (H_1) accepted indicating that capacity building promotes employees' performance and efficiency in service, which in turn enhances the chances of organization achieving their stated goals. He argued that the adoption of capacity building has improve the operating efficiency of the service sector as well as created more investment opportunities, business prospect and a more friendly business environment.

However, Ojokuku and Adegbite (2014) conducted a research "The Impact of capacity building and Manpower development in selected organization in Nigeria'. The survey research was employed for the study and data was gathered from 128 managers of randomly selected firms in South Western Nigeria with the aid of structured questioned and analyzed using descriptive statistics to examine the impact of capacity building on staff performance in selected organization in Nigeria. Based on the findings, they concluded that there is a strong positive relationship between capacity building and staff performance in an organization which implies that capacity building enhances employees' performance/service delivery which ultimately translates to improved organizational performance. Hence, capacity building is considered as important managerial issue in any organization because capacity building inputs and activities not only result in capacity building outputs (in the form of new knowledge, skills and management capabilities) but also contribute to the realization of other output target. It was therefore recommended that organizations should improve on their capacity building activities, so as to facilitate higher employee performance. Also, individual and workforce level capacity building activities should be within the context of and accompanied by strengthening of organization and systems that will be ensure the sustainability of activities, outputs and outcomes.

Agunyai (2014) studied the impact of Manpower development, Capacity building on service delivery in life -East Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria'. The main objective was to know whether efficient services delivery can be enhanced through prompt training and manpower development of local governments' staff in Nigeria. The research adopted both the quantitative and qualitative method of primary data whereby 117 people were selected using the stratified random sampling based on the reason that have adequate knowledge of how services are provided and can also ascertain if service delivery is efficient or not. He found out that the problem of poor database that is needed for manpower planning is a major hindrance or effective manpower development, training and capacity building of staff in Nigeria and as well that staff training, their capacity development has not significantly promoted efficient service delivery in life East Local Government. He recommended the need for federal and state government to be

persuasive in making local government embraces well designed policies of manpower development and capacity building.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research adopted survey research design which is used to gather information on a population using structured questionnaire instruments which was produced and administered on the staff of Enugu State Civil Service Commission to elicit responses on capacity building and other appropriate information relating to service delivery.

Population of the Study

Population of employees in Enugu State Civil Service Commission is Seventy (70).

Table 3 Nominal Roll of Enugu State Civil Service Commission 2023

Departments/Cadres	Number of Males	Number of Females	Total
Directors	2	3	5
Secretary	1		1
Administrative Officer Cadre	1	3	4
Executive Officer Cadre	2	22	24
Data Processing Cadre	1	3	4
Account Officer Cadre		2	2
Planning, Research and Statistics	2	1	3
Secretarial Cadre		2	2
Driver/Mechanical Cadre	2		2
Store Officer Cadre	1		1
Information Officer Cadre	1		1
Clerical Officer Cadre	2	14	16
Cleaner	2		2
Watchman/Security Cadre	3		3
Total	20	50	70

Sample Size Determination

The research is a census study as it adopted the entire population. In line with this, Anakwe (2007) stipulates that a researcher may decide to study the entire population if the subject under study is less than 1000. In this case, it is less than 1000 and manageable. Hence, the population is few and there was no need for sampling.

Sources of Data

Data for the research is derived through primary source. This is the materials of statistical investigation collected by the researcher for a particular purpose. The primary source of data is generated through a well-structured questionnaire that is developed by the researcher with the help of the supervisor.

Primary data were sourced through structured questionnaire which reflect the objectives, research questions and hypothesis.

The questionnaire was prepared based on 5-point rating scale ranging from Strongly Agreed (5) to Strongly Disagreed (1).

Table 3.2 gives the details as follow:

Table 2: Scales for questionnaire responses

Codes	Description	Real limit of numbers
SA	Strongly Agreed	4.50-5.00
A	Agreed	3.50-4.49
U	Undecided	2.50-3.49
D	Disagreed	1.50-2.49
SD	Strongly Disagreed	0.50-1.49

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Validity of the Research Instrument

To ascertain the validity of the work, all the documents and data generated passed through the supervisor who scrutinized each item and made necessary modification to ensure its relevance to the subject of study.

The researcher also drew questionnaires implied by the research questions and statement of the problem. A draft copy of the questionnaire was given to the researcher’s supervisor for vetting to ensure its relevance to the subject matter and the coverage of the topic of study.

The research instruments were presented to my Supervisor as well as other experts who are Senior Lecturers in the Department of Public Administration Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University who painstakingly examined each of the instruments, made comments on their suitability or otherwise. The observed errors by the experts helped to modify some items and incorporate new ones. The various inputs incorporated enhanced the soundness and the accuracy of the instrument to measure what it intends to measure.

Reliability of Data

In testing the reliability of the instruments, the researcher employed the test-retest technique. Test-retest measures the consistency of result when a test is repeated on the same sample at different point in time.

Tools of Data Analysis

Data generated through questionnaires were analyzed using statistical analysis. Statistical analysis involves the organization and interpretation of data according to well-defined, systematic and mathematical procedures and rules. Data collected were presented using tables, means and simple frequency.

Data analysis is a practice in which raw data is ordered and organized so that useful information can be extracted from it. In analyzing the data collected, the researcher employed statistical mean tool in line with the research question.

It follows that, all mean responses of 3.0 and above were accepted while mean responses below 3.0 were rejected.

$$X = \frac{\sum FX}{N}$$

N

Where,

X = Mean

∑ = Summation

F = Frequency

X = Point on the scale

N = Total Number of respondents.

The mean of the weighted scale is obtained as follows

Hence, cut off mean is $5+4+3+2+1=15/5=3.0$

It follows that, all mean responses of 3.0 and above were accepted while mean responses below 3.0 were rejected.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Analysis of research questions

Research question 1: *To what extent does capacity building affect the quality of staff output in Enugu State civil service commission?*

Table 1: Responses from question one

Capacity building exposes the staff to modern use of technology

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagreed	1	1.9	2.0	2.0
	Undecided	2	3.8	4.0	6.0
	Agreed	26	50.0	52.0	58.0
	Strongly Agreed	21	40.4	42.0	100.0
	Total	50	96.2	100.0	
Total		50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question just one (1) respondent representing 2 percent Disagreed to the question, two (2) respondents representing 4 percent were indifference that is their responses were undecided, twenty-six (26) respondents representing 52 percent Agreed to the question, while twenty-one (21) respondents representing 42 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 2: Responses from question two

Capacity building gives room to staff maximum productivity in an organization

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agreed	32	61.5	64.0	64.0
	Strongly Agreed	18	34.6	36.0	100.0
	Total	50	96.2	100.0	
Total		50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question.

Thirty-two (32) respondents representing 64 percent Agreed to the question, while eighteen (18) respondents representing 36 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 3: Responses from question three

Capacity building enhances self-reliance

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agreed	29	55.8	58.0	58.0
	Strongly Agreed	21	40.4	42.0	100.0
	Total	50	96.2	100.0	
Total		50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question

Twenty-nine (29) respondents representing 58 percent Agreed to the question, while twenty-one (21) respondents representing 42 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 4: Responses from question four
Capacity building helps in reduction of waste and uncertainty

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agreed	30	57.7	60.0	60.0
Strongly Agreed	20	38.5	40.0	100.0
Total	50	96.2	100.0	
Total	50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question Thirty-two (30) respondents representing 60 percent Agreed to the question, while eighteen (20) respondents representing 40 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 5: Responses from question five
Capacity building enhances effective completion of job

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agreed	30	57.7	60.0	60.0
Strongly Agreed	20	38.5	40.0	100.0
Total	50	96.2	100.0	
Total	50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question Thirty (30) respondents representing 60 percent Agreed to the question, while twenty (20) respondents representing 40 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Research Question 2: to what extent does staff empowerment programmes affect employees' commitment to organization goal actualization in enugu state civil service commission?

Table 6: Responses from question six
Staff empowerment program increases staff morale in their daily work input

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Undecided	4	7.7	8.0	8.0
Agreed	20	38.5	40.0	48.0
Strongly Agreed	26	50.0	52.0	100.0
Total	50	96.2	100.0	
Total	50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question Four (4) respondent representing 8 percent Disagreed to the question, twenty (20) respondents representing 40 percent Agreed to the question, while twenty-six (26) respondents representing 52 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 7: Responses from question seven
Staff empowerment programmes like skill acquisition enhances staff commitment

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agreed	30	57.7	60.0	60.0
Strongly Agreed	20	38.5	40.0	100.0
Total	50	96.2	100.0	
Total	50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question
Thirty (30) respondents representing 60 percent Agreed to the question, while twenty (20) respondents representing 40 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 8: Responses from question eight

Staff empowerment program increases the creative ability of the workers in the organization

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagreed	2	3.8	4.0	4.0
	Disagreed	7	13.5	14.0	18.0
	Undecided	2	3.8	4.0	22.0
	Agreed	27	51.9	54.0	76.0
	Strongly Agreed	12	23.1	24.0	100.0
Total		50	96.2	100.0	
Total		50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question. Two (2) respondents representing 4 percent strongly disagreed to the question above, Seven (7) respondent representing 14 percent Disagreed to the question, two (2) respondents representing 4 percent were indifference that is their responses were undecided, twenty-seven (27) respondents representing 54 percent Agreed to the question, while twelve (12) respondents representing 24 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 9: Responses from question nine

I get a feeling of satisfaction from my work after training

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagreed	1	1.9	2.0	2.0
	Disagreed	4	7.7	8.0	10.0
	Undecided	1	1.9	2.0	12.0
	Agreed	22	42.3	44.0	56.0
	Strongly Agreed	22	42.3	44.0	100.0
Total		50	96.2	100.0	
Total		50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question .one (1) respondents representing 2 percent strongly disagreed to the question above, four (4) respondent representing 8 percent Disagreed to the question, one (1) respondent representing 2 percent were indifference that is their responses were undecided, twenty-two (22) respondents representing 44 percent Agreed to the question, while twenty-two (22) respondents representing 44 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Table 10: Responses from question ten

Staff empowerment encourages loyalty to the organization

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagreed	4	7.7	8.0	8.0
	Undecided	1	1.9	2.0	10.0
	Agreed	26	50.0	52.0	62.0
	Strongly Agreed	19	36.5	38.0	100.0
Total		50	96.2	100.0	
Total		50	100.0		

Source: SPSS Version 23

The table above show how the respondents responded to the question
Just four (4) respondent representing 8 percent Disagreed to the question, one (1) respondent representing 2 percent were indifference that is their responses were undecided, twenty-six (26) respondents

representing 52 percent Agreed to the question, while nineteen (19) respondents representing 38 percent Strongly Agreed to the question.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 11: Test of Hypotheses One

Ho: Capacity building does not affect the quality of employee output in Enugu State Civil Service Commission.

Statistics					
	Capacity building exposes the staff to modern use of technology	Capacity building gives room to staff maximum productivity in an organization	Capacity building enhances self-reliance	Capacity building helps in reduction of waste and uncertainty	Capacity building enhances effective completion of job
N Valid	50	50	50	50	50
Mean	4.3400	4.3600	4.4200	4.4000	4.4000
Std. Deviation	.65807	.48487	.49857	.49487	.49487
Sum	217.00	218.00	221.00	220.00	220.00

Source: SPSS Version 23

The test of hypothesis one shows that the respondents accepted five of the items with mean scores of 4.34, 4.36, 4.42, 4.40, and 4.40 respectively from questions one to five (1-5). With a grand mean of 4.38 which is above the acceptable level of effectiveness 3.0. It indicates that the result above shows that capacity building affects the quality of staff output in Enugu state civil service commission.

Table 12: Test of hypotheses two

Ho: Staff empowerment programmes have no effect on employee commitment to goal actualization in Enugu State Civil Service Commission.

Statistics					
	Staff empowerment program increases staff morale in their daily work input	Staff empowerment programmes like skill acquisition enhances staff commitment	Staff empowerment program increases the creative ability of the workers in the organization	I get a feeling of satisfaction from my work after training	Staff empowerment encourages loyalty to the organization
N Valid	50	50	50	50	50
Mean	4.4400	4.4000	3.8000	4.2000	4.2000
Std. Deviation	.64397	.49487	1.08797	.96890	.83299
Sum	222.00	220.00	190.00	210.00	210.00

Source: SPSS Version 23

The test of hypothesis one shows that the respondents accepted five of the items with mean scores of 4.44, 4.40, 3.80, 4.20, and 4.20 respectively from questions six to ten (6-10). With a grand mean of 4.21 which is above the acceptable level of effectiveness 3.0. It indicates that the result above shows that staff empowerment programs affects employees' commitment to organizational goal actualization in Enugu State Civil Service Commission.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Capacity building plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of staff output within the Enugu State Civil Service Commission. By providing employees with opportunities to acquire and update their skills, the organization can expect improved job performance and increased efficiency. Staff empowerment

programs have a significant positive impact on employee commitment to organizational goal actualization in Enugu State Civil Service Commission.

Capacity building significantly contributes to employee career progression within Enugu State Civil Service Commission. By providing employees with the tools and knowledge they need to excel in their roles, the organization can foster professional growth and development.

Based on the results, the study recommended the followings;

1. It is recommended that the Enugu State Civil Service Commission continues to invest in capacity building initiatives for its employees. These initiatives should be tailored to address specific skill gaps and job requirements. Regular assessments of the impact of capacity building programs on staff output should be conducted to ensure their effectiveness and relevance.
2. Secondly, the Enugu State Civil Service Commission continues to implement and expand staff empowerment programs. This may include providing opportunities for employees to participate in decision-making, fostering a culture of open communication, and creating clear pathways for career progression and skill development.

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